

A Proofs for Section 2 (Preliminaries)

Lemma 2. *Let $N = (V, E_S \cup E_T)$ be a galled LGT network and let $v \in V(N)$ be a node with two distinct descendants x and y that are transfer nodes (with $v \in \{x, y\}$ being possible). Then one of the transfer edges incident to x or y has both endpoints in the subtree $\mathcal{T}_N(v)$.*

Proof. We prove this by contraposition. Let x' and y' be nodes that share a transfer edge with x and y , respectively. Suppose that neither x' nor y' are contained in $\mathcal{T}_N(v)$. Write $\text{lca}(a, b)$ for the lowest common ancestor of a, b in \mathcal{T}_N . By our supposition, in \mathcal{T}_N we have that v is on the path from $\text{lca}(x, x')$ to x , and from $\text{lca}(y, y')$ to y . This implies the existence of two underlying cycles in N : there is a cycle formed by $\text{lca}(x, x') - x' - x - \text{lca}(x, x')$ and the cycle formed by $\text{lca}(y, y') - y' - y - \text{lca}(y, y')$ (where the edges between x' and x , and between y' and y are used, and the rest use edges of \mathcal{T}_N). These cycles are distinct since they use a different (unique) transfer edge. However, they intersect at v , and thus N is not galled. \square

Lemma 3. *Let $N = (V, E_S \cup E_T)$ be a galled LGT network. Let $x, y \in V$ be two nodes that are not comparable in \mathcal{T}_N and such that x reaches y in N . Then there exists an edge $(x', y') \in E_T$ such that $x' \preceq_{\mathcal{T}_N} x$ and $y \preceq_{\mathcal{T}_N} y'$.*

Proof. Suppose for a contradiction that such (x', y') does not exist in N . Since x reaches y in N , we know that there must exist at least another node $w \in V(N)$ incomparable to both x and y that serves as an intermediary node from x to y . More specifically, there exists a transfer edge with an endpoint in $\mathcal{T}_N(x)$ and whose receiving end is w . Nevertheless, y is not a descendant of w (otherwise, $w = y'$ would end the proof), which implies the existence of a transfer edge from some descendant of w to a node incomparable with w . However this creates a situation where $\mathcal{T}_N(w)$ is a subtree with two transfer edges that have their endpoints outside of the subtree, which is forbidden by Lemma 2 \square

B Proofs for Section 3 (The Galled Completion Problem)

Lemma 4. *Let N be a galled-completion of a tree T that explains \mathcal{C} . Let $C \in \mathcal{C}$ be a character and let w be an origin for C in N . Then there is $\alpha_i \in \alpha_T(C)$ such that both of the following hold:*

- either $w \preceq \alpha_i$ or w is a transfer node whose child in \mathcal{T}_N is α_i .
- for every $\alpha_j \in \alpha_T(C) \setminus \{\alpha_i\}$ there is a transfer edge (u, v) such that $u \preceq w$ and $v = p_N(\alpha_j)$.

Proof. We focus on the first condition. First observe that if $v \in V(T)$, then $v \in V(N)$ as well. Moreover, the parent p_v of v in T is either also the parent of v in \mathcal{T}_N , or the latter is a transfer node created to complete T into N . In the latter case, note that at most one transfer node could be present on the path between p_v and v in \mathcal{T}_N , as otherwise, there would be two consecutive

transfer nodes which, as one can check, would violate Lemma 2. In other words, some edges of T are subdivided to obtain \mathcal{T}_N , but each edge can be subdivided at most once.

Let us next observe that if w is an origin for C , by definition it must be a node in $N - F_C(N)$, which is a graph that only contains FA nodes of T , their support tree descendants in N , and possibly transfer nodes that are the parents of FA nodes. Thus either w descends from some $\alpha_i \in \alpha_T(C)$, or results from a subdivision of $(p_T(\alpha_i), \alpha_i)$. In the latter case, w is the parent of α_i since an edge can only be subdivided once, as explained above. Therefore, the first condition of our statement holds.

For the second condition, as we know the origin w descends from some α_i or is its parent. Let α_j be a FA other than α_i . Let l be a leaf descending from α_j in \mathcal{T}_N . Since w is an origin, it reaches l in $N - F_C(N)$ and thus also in N . As w is not an ancestor of l , by Lemma 3 there is a transfer edge (u, v) in N such that $u \preceq w$ and $l \preceq v$ in \mathcal{T}_N . The endpoints of this transfer edge must also be in $N - F_C(N)$ for w to be able to use it. Next, note that $p_T(\alpha_j)$ has descendants not in C . Thus in N , $p_T(\alpha_j)$ and its support tree ancestors are in $F_C(N)$, and so it follows that v descends from α_j or is a transfer node on its parent edge, in which case $v = p_N(\alpha_j)$ (again since edges can only be subdivided once). If α_j is a leaf, the latter must hold and we are done. So assume that α_j is not a leaf and let l_1, l_2 be two leaves descending from α_j in \mathcal{T}_N . Then there are two transfer edges (u_1, v_1) and (u_2, v_2) that exist in $N - F_C(N)$, where u_1, u_2 descend from w and v_1, v_2 are ancestors of l_1 and l_2 , respectively. Since these two transfers go out of the $\mathcal{T}_N(w)$ subtree, they must in fact be equal by Lemma 2. In other words, w reaches every leaf below α_j through a single transfer (u, v) such that v is an ancestor of all those leaves. Since v is in $N - F_C(N)$, it follows that v must be the parent of α_j (and not α_j itself because it cannot be a transfer node as it has at least two children, by assumption on T). \square

Lemma 5. *Let T be a galled-completable tree for a character set \mathcal{C} . Then $|\alpha_T(C)| \leq 2$ for any character $C \in \mathcal{C}$.*

Proof. Let N be a galled-completion of T that explains \mathcal{C} . Suppose for contradiction that $|\alpha_T(C)| \geq 3$ for some $C \in \mathcal{C}$. Let w be an origin for C in $N - F_C(N)$. By Lemma 4, w descends from or is the parent of one of the FAs, say $x \in \alpha_T(C)$. Let y, z be two other FAs of C . Note that, by definition of FAs, x, y, z are pairwise incomparable in T . By the second statement of Lemma 4, there are transfer edges $(u_1, p_N(y))$ and $(u_2, p_N(z))$ where u_1 and u_2 descend from w in \mathcal{T}_N . This implies that the subtree $\mathcal{T}_N(w)$ contains two outgoing transfers, which contradicts Lemma 2. Thus $|\alpha_T(C)| \leq 2$ for all $C \in \mathcal{C}$. \square

Lemma 6. *Let T be a galled-completable tree for \mathcal{C} . Suppose that there exists two distinct characters A and B with $\alpha_T(A) = \{a_1, a_2\}$ and $\alpha_T(B) = \{b_1, b_2\}$. Then the two following statements hold:*

1. *If $b_1 \prec a_1$ and b_2 is not comparable to a_1 , then $a_2 = b_2$.*
2. *If $a_1 = b_1$, then either $b_2 \prec a_2$ or $a_2 \prec b_2$.*

Proof. We begin with the first statement. Suppose for a contradiction that the conditions of the lemma hold, but that $a_2 \neq b_2$. Let N be a galled-completion of T that explains \mathcal{C} . This leads to the following two cases.

- *Case 1:* a_2 and b_2 are comparable. Suppose $b_2 \prec a_2$. Let w be an origin for A in $N - F_A(N)$. By Lemma 4, w descends from a_1 or a_2 , or is a transfer node with one of those as a child. Suppose first that $w \preceq a_1$ or $w = p_N(a_1)$. We know by Lemma 4 that there exists a transfer edge from some descendant of w that has $p_N(a_2)$ as endpoint. Also by Lemma 4, $p_N(b_2)$ or a descendant of b_2 is a transfer node whose other endpoint is $p_N(b_1)$ or a descendant of b_1 . This implies that there are two transfer nodes in the subtree $\mathcal{T}_N(p_N(a_2))$ whose other endpoint is outside, which is forbidden by Lemma 2. The case where $w \preceq a_2$ or is the parent of a_2 is symmetric. Next suppose that $a_2 \prec b_2$. By Lemma 4, one of $p_N(a_1)$ or $p_N(a_2)$ is the receiving end of a transfer, whose sending end is on the other side. If $p_N(a_1)$ is a transfer node, we also know that $p_N(b_1)$ or one of its descendants is a transfer node, with the other endpoint on the b_2 side. Either way, $\mathcal{T}_N(p_N(a_1))$ has two descending transfer nodes with external endpoints, contradicting Lemma 4. Thus $p_N(a_2)$ is the receiving end of a transfer. By a symmetric argument, $p_N(b_1)$ is the receiving end of a transfer. This implies that there are transfers between $\mathcal{T}_N(a_1)$ and $\mathcal{T}_N(b_2)$ (or their parents) going in opposite directions. Because transfer edges are unidirectional, these transfers are distinct, from which it can easily be seen that there are two underlying cycles intersecting. Therefore, this case is not possible.
- *Case 2:* a_2 and b_2 are incomparable. By Lemma 4, there is one transfer with one endpoint being $p_N(a_1)$ or a descendant of a_1 , and the other being $p_N(a_2)$ or a descendant of a_2 . Likewise, there is a similar transfer connecting b_1 and b_2 . Since a_2 and b_2 are incomparable, these two transfers must be distinct, they are both in $\mathcal{T}_N(a_1)$ or $\mathcal{T}_N(p_N(a_1))$, and they both have external endpoints, contradicting Lemma 2.

Since neither case is possible, we must have $a_2 = b_2$.

Next, consider the second statement. Let N be a galled-completion of T that explains \mathcal{C} . Suppose for a contradiction that $a_1 = b_1$, but neither $a_2 \prec b_2$ nor $b_2 \prec a_2$ holds i.e. a_2 and b_2 are incomparable in \mathcal{T}_N . By Lemma 4, there is a transfer edge between descendants of a_1 and a_2 (or their parents), and a transfer edge between descendants of b_1 and b_2 (or their parents). Since a_2 and b_2 are incomparable, these transfers must be distinct. However, they imply the existence of two transfer nodes descending from $a_1 = b_1$ (or its parent) that have an external endpoint, contradicting Lemma 2. \square

Lemma 7. *Let T be a tree on leafset \mathcal{S} and character set \mathcal{C} . If T is galled-completable, then in the redundancy-free network $N = (V_T, E_T)$ of T , every node is incident to at most one transfer edge.*

Proof. Suppose for contradiction that some node u' of N is incident to two distinct transfer edges, with v', w' the other endpoints of those edges (note that

$v' = w'$ is possible). By construction, u', v', w' are subdivision vertices of \mathcal{T}_N , and are respective parents of FA nodes u, v, w in T . Moreover, v and w must be FA neighbors of u , and so there are characters C_{uv} (resp. C_{uw}) with FAs $\{u, v\}$ (resp. $\{u, w\}$) in T .

Suppose first that $v \neq w$. In that case, C_{uv} and C_{vw} are distinct as their FAs differ. By the second part of Lemma 6, the two characters C_{uv} and C_{uw} have a common FA u , and thus v and w are comparable. Suppose without loss of generality that $w \prec_T v$. We can further assume that w is a minimal FA neighbor of u (otherwise, we choose w to be such a neighbor, which does not affect the presence of the edge between u' and v'), which guarantees that $(w', u') \in E_T$. By the construction of N , the edge (v', u') cannot be in E_T , as u' only receives transfers from its minimal neighbors. Therefore, the transfer between u' and v' is in the (u', v') direction. As v is not in a simple pair, this edge is present because v has multiple FA neighbors and u is minimal. This means that there is another character C_{vz} with FAs $\{v, z\}$, where $z \neq u$. Using Lemma 6 in the same way as before, we get $u \prec_T z$. We now have two pairs of FAs $\{z, v\}$ and $\{u, w\}$, where $u \prec_T z$, w is not comparable to z (because v is not), and $w \neq v$. By putting $\{z, v\} = \{a_1, a_2\}$ and $\{u, w\} = \{b_1, b_2\}$, we obtain a contradiction of the first part of Lemma 6.

So suppose that $v = w$, and hence $C_{uv} = C_{uw}$. This means that both edges (u', v') and (v', u') are present. This is not possible if $\{u, v\}$ is simple, so u, v both have at least two FA neighbors, v must be a minimal FA neighbor of u and u a minimal FA neighbor of v . Let $x \neq v$ be another FA neighbor of u . Then some character C_{ux} has $\{u, x\}$ as FAs. Since C_{uv} has FAs $\{u, v\}$, by the second part of Lemma 6, x and v must be comparable. Since v is minimal, $v \prec_T x$. As v also has other FA neighbors, by a symmetric argument, some character C_{vy} has FAs $\{v, y\}$ with $u \prec_T y$. But the pair of FAs $\{y, v\}, \{u, x\}$ has $u \prec_T y$, x incomparable to y ($x \prec_T y$ is not possible since v would descend from y , and $y \prec_T x$ is not possible as u would descend from x), and $v \neq x$, a contradiction of the first part of Lemma 6. \square

Lemma 8. *A tree T on leafset \mathcal{S} with character set \mathcal{C} is galled-completable if and only if its redundancy-free network $N = (V, E_S \cup E_T)$ is a galled tree.*

Proof. (\Rightarrow) Suppose that T is galled-completable and let $N' = (V', E'_S \cup E'_T)$ be a galled-completion for T that explains \mathcal{C} . We need to show that N is a galled tree. We assume that N' is obtained from T by subdividing every edge once, then adding a set of transfer edges between subdivision nodes (note that if N' exists, such a galled-completion also exists). Since N also subdivides every edge once, this allows us to assume that N' and N have the same set of nodes, putting the nodes in correspondence without ambiguity.

We first map each transfer edge (u', v') of N to a distinct transfer edge (x, y) of N' , such that $y \in \{u', v'\}$. Let $(u', v') \in E_T$. Note that by the construction of N , u', v' are subdivision nodes of \mathcal{T}_N and are parents of FAs u, v . Moreover, u, v are FA neighbors, and thus there is some character C with $\alpha_T(C) = \{u, v\}$. By Lemma 4, in N' there is a transfer edge (x, y) , where either $x \preceq_{\mathcal{T}_N} u'$ and

$y = v'$, or $x \preceq_{\mathcal{T}_N} v'$ and $y = u'$. Either way, we map (u', v') to (x, y) . Note that by Lemma 7, u' and v' are only incident to one transfer edge (u', v') . Therefore, only (u', v') can be mapped to (x, y) , as $y \in \{u', v'\}$.

Next, consider $(u', v') \in E_T$ and its corresponding edge (x, y) in N' . Suppose that $(x, y) = (\tilde{u}, v')$ for some descendant \tilde{u} of u' in $\mathcal{T}_{N'}$. Consider the network \tilde{N} obtained from N' by removing (\tilde{u}, v') and inserting (u', v') (which does nothing if $\tilde{u} = u'$). Note that in N' , the transfer edge (\tilde{u}, v') belongs to a unique underlying cycle H formed by the transfer edge, plus the paths from \tilde{u} and from v' to the lowest common ancestor of \tilde{u} and v' in $\mathcal{T}_{N'}$. Since u' is on the path between that ancestor and \tilde{u} , in \tilde{N} the incorporation of (u', v') only creates an underlying cycle whose set of vertices is a subset of H . Since H did not intersect with other underlying cycles in N' , this new underlying cycle does not either, and it follows that \tilde{N} is a galled tree as well. The same idea applies if $y = u'$ instead.

Since all underlying cycles of N' are independent, we can apply the transformation from the previous paragraph to every mapped transfer edge of N' . Notice that because each $(u', v') \in E_T$ maps to a distinct transfer edge of N' , no edge of N' is “moved” twice by this process. Therefore, we obtain a galled tree whose set of transfer edges contains E_T . It then follows that N is a galled tree as well.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that the redundancy-free network N is a galled tree. We show that for every character in $C \in \mathcal{C}$ there exists a node in $N - F_C(N)$ that reaches every leaf in C as required by Lemma 1. Note that if $|\alpha_N(C)| = 1$, then C forms a clade in T and thus in \mathcal{T}_N . If u is the FA node of C in T , then u is able to reach every element of C in $N - F_C(N)$ since every support tree descendant of u is also in $N - F_C(N)$, which is sufficient to explain C .

Suppose that $|\alpha_T(C)| = 2$. Let u and v be the FAs of C in T , which are the roots of clades C_1 and C_2 such that $C = C_1 \cup C_2$. Denote $p_u = p_{\mathcal{T}_N}(u)$ and $p_v = p_{\mathcal{T}_N}(v)$, where p_u and p_v are transfer nodes since every edge of T was subdivided to produce N . Note that by definition, in \mathcal{T}_N all the descendants of p_u and of p_v are in C , and thus both of them appear in $N - F_C(N)$. Suppose that one of the edges (p_u, p_v) or (p_v, p_u) is present. In the first case, p_u is an origin for C and in the second case, p_v is an origin.

So suppose that neither transfer edge is present. Then by construction, either u or v has at least two FA neighbors (otherwise, we would have added one of the two edges between their parent in an arbitrary direction and be in the previous case). Suppose without loss of generality that u has at least two FA neighbors. Then v is not one of its minimal FA neighbors, which means that there is some minimal FA neighbor w of u such that $w \prec_T v$. Let $p_w = p_{\mathcal{T}_N}(w)$ and note that N contains the transfer edge (p_w, p_u) . Then, v is an origin for C , since it is in $N - F_C(N)$, it can reach all the elements of C that descend from itself in \mathcal{T}_N , and all those that descend from u through the transfer arc (p_w, p_u) .

We have therefore shown that all characters have an origin, which by Lemma 1 implies that N is a PTN for \mathcal{C} , as desired. \square

Theorem 1. *Algorithm 1 correctly solves the GALLED TREE COMPLETION problem in time $O(|V(T)||\mathcal{C}|)$.*

Proof. We begin by arguing that the algorithm is correct. The first *for* loop in Line 4 ensures that each character has at most two FAs as stated in Lemma 5. We claim that the second *for* loop will find all the required minimal transfers. For a fixed node v , we traverse its set of FA neighbors, noting that those are not necessarily comparable. However, if v has two incomparable FA neighbors, then v must also have at least two *minimal* incomparable FA neighbors. This then implies that the redundancy-free network N will have two transfer edges incident to $p_N(v)$, a contradiction of Lemma 7. Thus, Line 12 allows us to rule out these cases. After we ensure that all the FA neighbors of v are comparable we will find the minimum among them, which will allow us to add the desired transfer edge. For simple characters on the other hand, the verification in Line 20 allows us to add an arbitrary direction only when its unique neighbor is a marked node. The reason for this is that whenever the node is marked we know that there do not exist other FA neighbors to compare c_{min} to.

Let us now argue the complexity. Let $T = (V, E)$ be the given tree. The complexity will be dominated by the first *for* loop. For a given character $C \in \mathcal{C}$, computing the FAs can be done in time $O(|V|)$. Thus the first *for* can be done in time $O(|\mathcal{C}||V|)$. On the other hand, the postorder traversal of T that adds the transfer edges can be done on time $O(|V| + |\mathcal{C}|)$ since we know that every node can have at most $|\mathcal{C}| - 1$ FA neighbors, as characters determine FA neighbors. Finally, the last verification on Line 21 can be done in time $O(|V|)$ (see e.g. [18]).

C Proofs for Section 4 (The Galled Compatibility Problem)

Lemma 9. *Suppose that \mathcal{C} contains a maximal character C that is compatible with every other character. Let $\mathcal{C}_1 = \{A \in \mathcal{C} : A \subset C\}$ and $\mathcal{C}_2 = \{A \in \mathcal{C} : A \cap C \neq \emptyset\}$. Then \mathcal{C} is galled-compatible if and only if \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 are both galled-compatible.*

Moreover, given galled PTNs N_1, N_2 that explain $\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2$, respectively, one can obtain in time $O(|\mathcal{C}|)$ a galled PTN N that explains \mathcal{C} .

Proof. The first direction of the if and only if statement is trivial: if \mathcal{C} is galled-compatible, then any of its subset is galled-compatible, including \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 , since a network that explains \mathcal{C} also explains $\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2$. In the other direction, suppose that \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 are galled-compatible. Since C is compatible with every character, for any $A \in \mathcal{C} \setminus \{C\}$, one of $A \subseteq C, C \subseteq A$, or $A \cap C \neq \emptyset$ holds. Also, because C is maximal, $C \subseteq A$ does not hold. It follows that A is in one of \mathcal{C}_1 or \mathcal{C}_2 and thus $\{\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2\}$ is a partition of $\mathcal{C} \setminus \{C\}$. Moreover, by defining $S_1 := \bigcup_{A \in \mathcal{C}_1} A$ and $S_2 := \bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{C}_2} B$, we get that $S_1 \cap C = \emptyset$ and $S_2 \subseteq C$. In particular, S_1 and S_2 are disjoint. Let N_1 and N_2 be galled trees that explain \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 , respectively. Then $L(N_1)$ and $L(N_2)$ are also disjoint. Consider the network N obtained by (1) creating a root node r ; (2) adding $r(N_1)$ and $r(N_2)$ as children of r ; (3) for each $s \in C \setminus S_2$, adding s as a leaf child of $r(N_2)$. Observe that, since N_1 and N_2 are galled trees, by adding r and its two child edges cannot create intersecting

cycles, nor can adding leaves under $r(N_2)$. Moreover, it is not hard to see that every character of \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 is still explained by N , and C is also explained since it is a clade of N . Thus C is galled-compatible. This construction also shows how to obtain N from N_1 and N_2 in time $O(|C|)$, since it only requires adding a new root and adding up to $|C|$ leaves under $r(N_2)$.

Lemma 10. *Let T be a tree that is galled-completable for \mathcal{C} , and let $A, B \in \mathcal{C}$ be a pair of incompatible characters. Then one of the following holds:*

- A is split into $A \setminus B, A \cap B$ in T , and B is a clade of T ;
- B is split into $B \setminus A, A \cap B$ in T , and A is a clade of T .

Proof. Since A and B are incompatible, by definition T cannot contain both as a clade and so at most one can be. So assume for now that neither A nor B is a clade of T . Then both characters have two FAs in T (and not more, by Lemma 5). Let a_1, a_2 and b_1, b_2 be the FA nodes of A and B , respectively, and let A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2 be the respective clades of a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2 .

We claim that some a_i is a strict ancestor of some b_j or vice-versa. Note that $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$, so we may assume without loss of generality that $A_1 \cap B_1 \neq \emptyset$. Thus, a_1 has a descending leaf in common with b_1 , which implies that a_1 is an ancestor of b_1 or vice-versa. If $a_1 \neq b_1$, our claim holds. If $a_1 = b_1$, then $a_2 \prec b_2$ or $b_2 \prec a_2$ by Lemma 6 (part 2), and again our claim holds.

We may therefore assume, without loss of generality, that a_1 is a strict ancestor of b_1 , which implies $B_1 \subseteq A_1$. Notice that b_2 cannot be a descendant of a_1 , since otherwise we would have $B_2 \subseteq A_1$ and $B_1 \cup B_2 \subseteq A_1$, contradicting the incompatibility of A and B . Since b_2 is incomparable with b_1 , it is also incomparable with a_1 . Then by Lemma 6 (part 1), $a_2 = b_2$. Those imply $B_1 \subseteq A_1$ and $A_2 = B_2$, in turn implying $B \subseteq A$ and contradicting that A and B are incompatible.

This establishes that exactly one of A or B is a clade of T . Suppose that B is a clade and that A is split into A_1 and A_2 in T , with respective FAs a_1, a_2 . Let b be the (unique) FA of B . If $b \preceq a_1$ or $b \preceq a_2$, then $B \subseteq A$ and A, B would be compatible. Moreover, B intersects with at least one of A_1 and A_2 since it intersects with A , and thus b is an ancestor of a_1 or a_2 . If b is an ancestor of both, then $A \subseteq B$ and again A, B would be compatible. Hence b is an ancestor of exactly one of a_1 or a_2 . If b is an ancestor of a_1 , then $A_1 = B \cap A$ and $A_2 = A \setminus B$. If b is an ancestor of a_2 , then $A_2 = B \cap A$ and $A_1 = A \setminus B$. This shows that the first case of the statement holds.

If A is a clade of T instead, then using the same arguments, we get the second case of the statement. \square

Lemma 11. *Let A be a maximal character of \mathcal{C} . Suppose that T is a galled-completable tree for \mathcal{C} in which A is split into the clades A_1 and A_2 . Let $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{C}$ be the subset of characters that intersect with both A_1 and A_2 .*

Then, after possibly exchanging the subscripts of A_1 and A_2 , \mathcal{X} is an (A_1, A_2) -chain. Moreover, for every $X \in \mathcal{X}$, the clades $X \cap A_1$ and $X \cap A_2$ are in T .

Proof. Let a_1, a_2 be the FAs of A , which respectively correspond to the clades A_1 and A_2 . Let $X \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{A\}$ and note that although X intersects with both A_1 and A_2 , it cannot contain both, as otherwise A would not be maximal. Thus one of $X \cap A_1 \subset A_1$ or $X \cap A_2 \subset A_2$ holds.

If $X \cap A_1 \subset A_1$, then a_1 has descending leaves not in X , implying that X has a FA x_1 that strictly descends from a_1 . Since X also intersects with A_2 , X has another FA x_2 that must be incomparable with a_1 and, by Lemma 6 (part 1), the other FA x_2 of X is equal to a_2 . This implies $X \setminus A_1 = A_2$. If $X \cap A_2 \subset A_2$, then instead this argument yields $x_1 = a_1, x_2 \prec a_2$ and $X \cap A_2 \subset A_2, X \setminus A_2 = A_1$. Suppose for the remainder that $x_1 \prec a_1$ and $x_2 = a_2$. This is without loss of generality, as otherwise we can swap the subscripts of A_1 and A_2 .

Next, consider another character $X' \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{X, A\}$. As above, X' must have two FAs x'_1, x'_2 with either $x'_1 \prec a_1$ and $x'_2 = a_2$, or vice-versa. By the latter case, we mean $x'_2 \prec a_2$ and $x'_1 = a_1$, which we claim cannot occur. If this were true, we get $x_1 \prec a_1 = x'_1$ while $x_2 = a_2 \neq x'_2$, contradicting Lemma 6 (part 1). It must then be that $x'_1 \prec a_1$ and $x'_2 = a_2$.

It follows that every $X' \in \mathcal{X}$ has a FA equal to a_2 . By Lemma 6 (part 2), the FAs other than a_2 of two characters of \mathcal{X} are comparable and, by the above, descend from a_1 . Therefore, the FAs on the a_1 side are pairwise-comparable in terms of strict ancestry. This implies that in T , there is a path from a_1 to one of its descendants that contains all the FAs of the elements of \mathcal{X} on the a_1 side. By listing these FAs from the deepest up until a_1 , we get an ordering $X_1, \dots, X_l = A$ of \mathcal{X} such that $X_1 \cap A_1 \subset X_2 \cap A_1 \subset \dots \subset X_l \cap A_1 = A_1$. Also, the FAs on the a_2 side are all equal to a_2 , which means that $X \setminus A_1 = A_2$ for each X of \mathcal{X} .

It follows that \mathcal{X} is an (A_1, A_2) -chain, and that each $X \cap A_1$ and each $X \cap A_2 = A_2$ forms a clade in T . \square

Lemma 12. *Let A be a maximal character of \mathcal{C} . Suppose that T is a galled-completable tree for \mathcal{C} in which A is split into the clades A_1 and A_2 . Let $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{C}$ be the subset of characters that intersect with both A_1 and A_2 and suppose that \mathcal{X} is an (A_1, A_2) -chain. Let $X_1 \cap A_1$ be the bottom of the chain and let A_2 be the stable side of the chain.*

If $C \in \mathcal{C} \setminus \mathcal{X}$ contains $X_1 \cap A_1$ or contains A_2 , then C is a clade of T .

Proof. Suppose that C contains $X_1 \cap A_1$. If $C = X_1 \cap A_1$, then T contains C by Lemma 11. Otherwise, C is a strict superset of $X_1 \cap A_1$. Note that since $C \notin \mathcal{X}$ and already intersects with A_1 , C does not intersect with A_2 . However, $X_1 \setminus A_1 = A_2$ by the definition of an (A_1, A_2) -chain. Therefore, $C \setminus X_1$ and $X_1 \setminus C$ are non-empty, which implies that C and X_1 are incompatible. By Lemma 10, one of C or X_1 must be a clade of T . We know that X_1 is already split into $X_1 \cap A_1$ and $X_1 \cap A_2$ in T , and thus C must be a clade of T .

Suppose that C contains A_2 . If $C = A_2$, then T contains C as a clade by assumption. Otherwise, C is a strict superset of $A_2 = X_1 \cap A_2$. As before, C does not intersect with A_1 , and thus does not intersect with $X_1 \cap A_1$ and is therefore incompatible with X_1 . Again, C is a clade of T by Lemma 10. \square

Lemma 13. *Let A be a maximal character of \mathcal{C} and suppose that there is a galled-completable tree T^* for \mathcal{C} in which A is split into A_1 and A_2 . Let T be the tree whose set of clades is precisely the clades forced by $\{A_1, A_2\}$ (plus the root clade and the leaves).*

If $C \in \mathcal{C}$ is a character not forced by $\{A_1, A_2\}$, then all the taxa in C have the same parent in T .

Proof. Let T and T^* be as defined in the lemma statement. Also, let \mathcal{X} be the set of characters that intersect both A_1 and A_2 . By Lemma 11, we may assume that \mathcal{X} forms an (A_1, A_2) -chain. Let $X_1 \in \mathcal{X}$ be such that $X_b := X_1 \cap A_1$ is the bottom of the chain, and $X_s := X_1 \setminus A_1 = A_2$ is the stable side (using the subscripts b for bottom and s for stable). Let x_b be root node of the X_b clade in T and let x_s be the root node of the X_s clade.

By Lemma 12, T^* contains all the clades forced by $\{A_1, A_2\}$. Thus T^* contains all the clades of T , plus possibly others. We assume that a clade present in both T and T^* is rooted at the same node in both trees — that is, if y is the root of some clade Y of T , then y is also present in T^* and is the root of clade Y in T^* as well. We will therefore assume that $V(T) \subseteq V(T^*)$. Notably, T^* also contains X_b and X_s , so we assume that the same nodes x_b and x_s are the roots of these clades in T^* as well.

Before proceeding, we establish a fact on the structure of T (as can be seen in Figure 7 below).

Fact 1. Every internal node of T is an ancestor of x_b or x_s , and the root of T is the only node that is an ancestor of both.

Proof We claim that every non-trivial clade of T is either a (not necessarily strict) superset of X_b or of X_s (a trivial clade is either a single element or all of $L(T)$). Recall that we can distinguish three types of forced clades in T : (1) forced clades of the form $X \cap A_1$ for $X \in \mathcal{X}$, which by the chain properties must be supersets of $X_1 \cap A_1 = X_b$; (2) forced clades of the form $X \cap A_2$, which are equal to $A_2 = X_s$; (3) forced clades from those those C' that contain X_b or X_s . In all cases, our claim holds.

Given this claim, notice that any non-root internal node v of T either roots the clade A_1 , A_2 , or it roots a forced clade. Since any such clade contains X_b or X_s , v must be an ancestor of x_b or x_s .

Now assume that a non-root node v has both x_b and x_s as descendants. Let a_1 be the root of the A_1 clade. Note that a_1 is an ancestor of x_b but not x_s , so a_1 is on the path from x_b to x_s . This implies that v is an ancestor of a_1 and thus the clade corresponding to v contains A_1 . As v is also an ancestor of x_s , which roots the A_2 clade, then the clade of v also contains A_2 . Thus, the clade of v contains $A_1 \cup A_2 = A$. By assumption, A is not a clade of T , so the clade of v is a strict superset of A . Moreover, since v is not a root, the clade of v must be in T because it was forced, implying the existence of a character in \mathcal{C} that strictly contains A , contradicting its maximality, thereby establishing our fact. \square

Observe that Fact 1 implies that in T , all the children of x_b and x_s are leaves. In fact, aside from the root, all the nodes on the path between x_b and x_s have a single non-leaf child, which is the one that leads to x_b or x_s .

Now suppose that some $C \in \mathcal{C}$ is not forced by $\{A_1, A_2\}$, but that there are $y, z \in C$ such that the parent p_y of y in T is different from the parent p_z of z in T . Assume without loss of generality that the distance between p_y and the root of T is smaller than or equal to the distance between p_z and the root. Since p_y and p_z are internal nodes of T , they are ancestors of x_b or x_s in T by Fact 1. Figure 6 illustrates one possible scenario where p_y is the root of T and p_z is on the path between the root and x_b . Note that $\{p_y, p_z\} = \{x_b, x_s\}$ is not possible, since otherwise C would intersect with both $X_b \subseteq A_1$ and $X_s \subseteq A_2$, in which case C should be in \mathcal{X} and be a forced character. Thus at least one of p_y or p_z is a strict ancestor of x_b or x_s in T . Since p_y is closer to the root, we may assume that this holds for p_y .

Next, consider T^* , and let $r = lca_{T^*}(x_b, x_s)$, that is, the lowest common ancestor of x_b and x_s in T^* . Note that because T^* can have more clades than T , r is not necessarily the root of T^* . Let P be the set of nodes of T^* on the path between r and x_b , or on the path between r and x_s , *excluding* x_b and x_s themselves.

Fact 2. Let N be any galled-completion of T^* that explains \mathcal{C} . Then there is an underlying cycle in N that contains all the nodes in P , plus possibly nodes that descend from x_b or x_s , but no other nodes.

Proof Since X_1 is split into X_b and X_s in T^* , by Lemma 4 there must be a transfer edge between $p_N(x_b)$ or a descendant of x_b , and $p_N(x_s)$ and a descendant of x_s , which implies that existence of the claimed cycle. \square

Fig. 7. An illustration of T versus T^* . The white circles represent clades that are common to T and T^* .

Our next step is to argue that because of y and z , there is some other cycle that intersects with P . To this end, define p'_y as the first ancestor of y in T^*

that has one of x_b or x_s as a descendant, and define p'_z as the first ancestor of z in T^* that has one of x_b or x_s as a descendant. Recall that p_y is the parent of y in T , but that p_y is also in T^* and represents the same clade, although p_y might not be the parent of y in T^* . But in T^* , p_y has y plus one of x_b or x_s as a descendant. Because of this, we have that p'_y is either equal to p_y , or it is a descendant of p_y (in T^*). Likewise, p'_z is a descendant of p_z in T^* . Figure 7 shows a case where p_y is a strict ancestor of p'_y and $p_z = p'_z$.

Fact 3. Let N be any galled-completion of T^* for \mathcal{C} . Then there is an underlying cycle in N that contains an ancestor of y not in P , plus all the nodes on the path between p'_y and p'_z .

Proof Let us first argue that p'_y is not a FA node for C in T^* : if this was the case, because p'_y has x_b or x_s as a descendant, having p'_y as a FA of C would imply that C contains X_b or X_s and it would be forced. Therefore, there is a FA node f_y of C that is a strict descendant of p'_y and an ancestor of y . Likewise, p'_z is not a FA of C either, and there is a FA f_z that is a strict descendant of p'_z and an ancestor of z .

Next, note that y is not a descendant of p_z in T , as otherwise p_y would descend from p_z and would be farther from the root. Since p_z still represents the same clade in T^* , the same holds in T^* . Then in T^* , since p'_z is a descendant of p_z , we deduce that $p'_y \neq p'_z$ (otherwise, we would have $y \prec_{T^*} p'_y = p'_z \preceq_{T^*} p_z$). Thus, f_y and f_z are distinct nodes. By Lemma 4, there is a transfer edge between these two FA subtrees. Because f_y and f_z strictly descend from a node in P , the endpoints of this transfer edge are not in P , implying the existence of a cycle that contains the created transfer nodes, along with the path from that node to p'_y , then the path from p'_y to p'_z , followed by the path from p'_z to the transfer node in that subtree. \square

We may conclude the proof with that last fact. Consider the cycle H obtained from Fact 2 that contains the nodes of P and possible descendants of x_s and x_b . Then consider the cycle H' obtained from Fact 3. The latter has an ancestor of y not in P , and because y does not descend from x_b or x_s , these two cycles are different. Moreover, H' contains p'_y . If p'_y is a node of P , then H and H' intersect, a contradiction. Otherwise, p'_y must be a strict ancestor of r . This can only occur if p_y was the root of T , and that p'_y ended up as an ancestor of $\text{lca}_{T^*}(x_b, x_s)$ when refining T to T^* . In this case however, p_z could not be the root of T as well, and p_z must be a descendant of r . Therefore, H' contains r and again, this implies that H and H' intersect, which concludes the proof.

Lemma 14. Let A be a maximal character of \mathcal{C} and let $\{A_1, A_2\}$ be a partition of A . Then there is a tree that is completable for \mathcal{C} and that contains the clades A_1 and A_2 if and only if all the following conditions hold:

1. Let \mathcal{X} be the characters that intersect with A_1 and A_2 . Then \mathcal{X} forms an (A_1, A_2) -chain;
2. There exists a tree T on leafset \mathcal{S} whose set of clades is precisely the set of clades forced by $\{A_1, A_2\}$ (plus the root clade and leaves).

3. Let \mathcal{C}_F be the set of characters forced by $\{A_1, A_2\}$. Then for any $C \in \mathcal{C} \setminus \mathcal{C}_F$, all the taxa of C have the same parent in T .
4. For any subset $\mathcal{C}' \subseteq \mathcal{C} \setminus \mathcal{C}_F$ such that all taxa that belong to some character of \mathcal{C}' have the same parent in T , \mathcal{C}' is galled-compatible.

Proof. Suppose that there is a tree T^* that contains the clades A_1, A_2 , such that T^* is galled-completable for \mathcal{C} . Condition 1 holds because by Lemma 11, \mathcal{X} forms an (A_1, A_2) -chain. For Condition 2, by Lemma 11 and 12, T^* contains all the clades forced by $\{A_1, A_2\}$, and therefore T as described in the condition must exist. Condition 3 holds by Lemma 13. Finally, Condition 4 holds because by the existence of T^* , we have that \mathcal{C} is galled-compatible. By heredity, any subset $\mathcal{C}' \subseteq \mathcal{C}$ is galled-compatible, including those described in the condition.

In the converse direction, assume that all the conditions of our statement hold. We show how to obtain a tree T^* with clades A_1 and A_2 that is galled-completable for \mathcal{C} . Let T be the tree whose set of clades consists of the clades forced by $\{A_1, A_2\}$. Let \mathcal{X} be the characters that intersect A_1 and A_2 . Let $X_1 \in \mathcal{X}$ such that $X_1 \cap A_1$ is the bottom of the chain and $X_1 \setminus A_1 = A_2$. We know that T has the clades $X_1 \cap A_1$ and A_2 , since they are forced. For later reference, we let x_b and x_s be the roots of these clades in T , respectively.

Next, for each internal node $v \in V(T)$, let \mathcal{C}_v be the characters whose taxa all have v as their parent in T . We know that \mathcal{C}_v is galled-compatible, so there is a tree T_v that is galled-completable for \mathcal{C}_v . We modify T as follows: remove every leaf that is a child of v , and add the root of T_v as a new child of v . After doing this for every v , we obtain the tree T^* .

We claim that T^* is galled-completable for \mathcal{C} . First, notice that T^* contains all the clades of T , since we have only removed leaves (trivial clades) and replaced them by subtrees, which does not remove clades that were already present in T . Thus every clade forced by $\{A_1, A_2\}$ is in T^* . In particular, $X_1 \cap A_1$ and A_2 are still clades of T^* , still rooted at x_b and x_s , respectively. Add a transfer arc from the parent branch of x_b to the parent branch of x_s . This yields a network that we call N .

Let \mathcal{C}_F be the characters forced by $\{A_1, A_2\}$. We will add further arcs to N , but for the moment we claim that N , with the single transfer arc $(p_N(x_b), p_N(x_s))$, explains the characters in \mathcal{C}_F . Recall that there are three types of forced clades, which we deal with as follows:

- let $C \in \mathcal{C}_F$ such that C contains the bottom of the chain, namely $X_1 \cap A_1$. Then C is a forced clade, which is in T and therefore in T^* . Thus T^* explains C without requiring any transfer.
- let $C \in \mathcal{C}_F$ such that C contains the stable side of the chain, namely A_2 . Again, C is forced in T and thus T^* and is also explained.
- let $C \in \mathcal{C}_F$ such that $C \in \mathcal{X}$. Then C intersects both A_1 and A_2 . By the definition of an (A_1, A_2) -chain, $C \cap A_1$ is either equal to $X_1 \cap A_1$, or it is a strict superset of $X_1 \cap A_1$. Also by the definition of chains, $C \cap A_2 = A_2$. We know that $C \cap A_1$ and $C \cap A_2$ are forced by $\{A_1, A_2\}$ and are thus present in T and T^* . The network N can explain C by putting the origin at the

root of the $C \cap A_1$ clade, and using the transfer arc $(p(x_b), p(x_s))$ to send the character to $C \cap A_2 = A_2$. Note that this is possible since $C \cap A_1$ is a superset of $X_1 \cap A_2$, and thus the root of the $C \cap A_1$ clade is an ancestor of $p(x_b)$, or is equal to x_b when $C = X_1$ (in which case the transfer can still be used).

It only remains to explain the characters not in \mathcal{C}_F . For each subtree T_v , replace T_v by a galled completion N_v that explains \mathcal{C}_v , which exists by assumption. This ensures that each character from each \mathcal{C}_v is explained by the resulting network. Moreover, since the T_v 's are independent subtrees, all additional cycles created are entirely contained inside the N_v subnetworks and, in particular, do not contain v . This implies that we do not create intersecting cycles that involve nodes from two distinct N_v subnetworks, and that do not intersect with the cycle involving $(p(x_b), p(x_s))$. Therefore, the resulting network is a galled tree. This concludes the proof. \square

Lemma 15. *Suppose that \mathcal{C} has no maximal character that is compatible with all the others. Then there exists a pair of incompatible characters $\{A, B\}$ of \mathcal{C} such that A and B are both maximal.*

Proof. Let A be a maximal character of \mathcal{C} . By assumption, there is some $B \in \mathcal{C}$ such that A and B are incompatible. Choose such a B of maximum cardinality. Note that $A \cap B$, $B \setminus A$, $A \setminus B$ are all non-empty. Suppose that B is not maximal, i.e. there is $B' \in \mathcal{C}$ such that $B \subset B'$. We have $A \cap B' \neq \emptyset$ because B' contains B . Also, $B' \subset A$ is not possible since $B \setminus A$ is non-empty, and $A \subset B'$ is not possible since A is maximal. Thus A and B' are incompatible, contradicting the choice of B . \square

Algorithm 2 is the full pseudocode of the galled-compatibility algorithm. The idea of the algorithm is as follows.

1. If \mathcal{C} has a maximal character C compatible with every character, then we know that we can simply recurse into \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 as in Lemma 9.
2. Otherwise, we must deal with maximal characters that are all incompatible. We choose incompatible A, B that are both maximal (shown to exist in Lemma 15).
3. We know that a galled-completable tree, if one exists, must contain the clades $A \setminus B$, $A \cap B$, or $B \setminus A$, $B \cap A$. We do not know which one it is, so we try the former first. That is, first consider the partition $\{A_1, A_2\} = \{A \setminus B, A \cap B\}$.
4. The function *tryPartition* checks whether it is possible to satisfy Conditions 1,2,3 from Lemma 14 with $\{A_1, A_2\}$ enforced. If one of those conditions fails, we know that A_1, A_2 cannot lead to a solution, and *tryPartition* returns “invalid partition”. When *getCilledTree* receives this answer, it attempts to check whether using $\{B_1, B_2\} = \{B \setminus A, B \cap A\}$ works instead, which is the only other possibility.

Do note that Lemma 14 only applies to maximal characters. Since we potentially check them on A and B , it is crucial to have both A and B as maximal characters.

```

1 function getGalledTree( $\mathcal{C}$ )
2   if  $\mathcal{C} = \emptyset$  then return true
3   if  $\mathcal{C}$  has a maximal character  $C$  compatible with every  $C' \in \mathcal{C}$  then
4     Let  $\mathcal{C}_1 = \{A \in \mathcal{C} : A \subset C\}$ ,  $\mathcal{C}_2 = \{A \in \mathcal{C} : A \cap C = \emptyset\}$ 
5     return getGalledTree( $\mathcal{C}_1$ )  $\wedge$  getGalledTree( $\mathcal{C}_2$ )
6
7   Let  $\{A, B\}$  be a pair of maximal incompatible characters from  $\mathcal{C}$ 
8   Let  $\{A_1, A_2\} = \{A \setminus B, A \cap B\}$ 
9   result = tryPartition( $\mathcal{C}$ ,  $\{A_1, A_2\}$ )
10  if result = “yes” then return true
11  if result = “no” then return false
12
13  //otherwise, result = “invalid partition”, try the other partition
14  Let  $\{B_1, B_2\} = \{B \setminus A, B \cap A\}$ 
15  result = tryPartition( $\mathcal{C}$ ,  $\{B_1, B_2\}$ )
16  if result = “yes” then return true, otherwise return false
17
18 function tryPartition( $\mathcal{C}$ ,  $\{A_1, A_2\}$ )
19   Let  $\mathcal{X}$  be the characters that intersect  $A_1$  and  $A_2$ 
20   if  $\mathcal{X}$  is not an  $(A_1, A_2)$ -chain nor an  $(A_2, A_1)$ -chain then return
21     “invalid partition”
22   Let  $\mathcal{C}_F$  and  $F$  be the characters and clades, respectively, forced by
23      $\{A_1, A_2\}$ 
24   Let  $T$  be the tree whose set of non-trivial clades is  $F$ 
25   if  $T$  does not exist then return “invalid partition”
26   if there is  $C \in \mathcal{C} \setminus \mathcal{C}_F$  and  $u, v \in C$  with distinct parents in  $T$  then return
27     “invalid partition”
28   foreach  $v \in V(T)$  do
29     Let  $\mathcal{C}_v \subset \mathcal{C} \setminus \mathcal{C}_F$  be the characters only containing taxa whose parent is
30        $v$ 
31     if  $\mathcal{C}_v \neq \emptyset \wedge$  getGalledTree( $\mathcal{C}_v$ ) = false then return “no”
32   return “yes”

```

Algorithm 2: Main galled-tree reconstruction algorithm.

5. If $\{A_1, A_2\}$ passes the three tests in *tryPartition*, then we check recursively that all the \mathcal{C}_v 's are galled-compatible. If they all are, we return “yes” and we are done. If some \mathcal{C}_v is not galled-compatible, then we know that A_1, A_2 cannot lead to a solution.

An important subtlety arises in this case. We do not return “invalid partition”, because this would lead to trying with $\{B_1, B_2\}$ instead. This could lead to an exponential time algorithm, because we would recurse into too many cases on both $\{A_1, A_2\}$ and $\{B_1, B_2\}$. Instead, we return “no”, and the main algorithm returns *false* without even trying $\{B_1, B_2\}$. This is correct, because if we find a \mathcal{C}_v that is not galled-compatible, we know that \mathcal{C} itself is not galled-compatible and there is no point in trying $\{B_1, B_2\}$.

The correctness and complexity details of the algorithm now follow.

Theorem 2. *Algorithm 2 correctly solves the GALLED COMPATIBILITY problem and runs in time $O(n|\mathcal{C}|^3)$.*

Proof. We first prove by induction on $|\mathcal{C}|$ that the algorithm always returns the correct answer. As a base case, when $|\mathcal{C}| = 0$, \mathcal{C} is trivially galled-compatible and the algorithm correctly returns true.

So suppose for the inductive step that $|\mathcal{C}| > 0$. If \mathcal{C} has a maximal compatible character C , then by Lemma 9, \mathcal{C} is galled-compatible if and only if \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 are galled-compatible. Since, by induction, the algorithm returns the correct answer on both \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 , returning $getGalledTree(\mathcal{C}_1) \wedge getGalledTree(\mathcal{C}_2)$ is correct.

So suppose that \mathcal{C} does not have a maximal compatible character. Note that by Lemma 15, the algorithm will find maximal incompatible A and B . First assume that \mathcal{C} is galled-compatible, in which case we need to argue that the algorithm returns true. Let T^* be a tree that is galled-completable for \mathcal{C} . By Lemma 10, T^* contains either the clades $\{A_1, A_2\} = \{A \setminus B, A \cap B\}$ or $\{B_1, B_2\} = \{B \setminus A, B \cap A\}$. Assume first that T^* contains A_1, A_2 . Then all the conditions of Lemma 14 hold for A_1, A_2 . Thus, all the conditions verified by *tryPartition* on input $\{A_1, A_2\}$ will succeed (including the calls to $getGalledTree(\mathcal{C}_v)$, which are assumed to return true by induction). It follows that *tryPartition* will return “yes” and that *getGalledTree* will correctly return true.

Next, assume instead that T^* contains the clades $\{B_1, B_2\}$. If Algorithm 2 gets to call *tryPartition*($\mathcal{C}, \{B_1, B_2\}$), then as in the previous case, we know that all the tests made by *tryPartition* will pass and that it will return “yes”. However, we will not reach that point if the prior call *tryPartition*($\mathcal{C}, \{A_1, A_2\}$) has returned “yes” or “no”. If that previous call returned “yes”, then *getGalledTree* will return true, which is actually the correct answer. A problem occurs if this previous call returned “no” on input $\{A_1, A_2\}$. By inspecting *tryPartition*, we see that this only occurs when there is a \mathcal{C}_v on which $getGalledTree(\mathcal{C}_v)$ returns false. By induction, this means that \mathcal{C}_v is not galled-compatible, implying in turn that \mathcal{C} is not galled-compatible, a contradiction. Thus, we may assume that *tryPartition* on input $\{A_1, A_2\}$ either returns “yes” (in which case we correctly return true), or “invalid partition”, in which case we correctly return true by then trying $\{B_1, B_2\}$.

In the converse direction, suppose that \mathcal{C} is not galled-compatible. Then one of the four conditions of Lemma 14 must fail on both $\{A_1, A_2\}$ and $\{B_1, B_2\}$. This means that on either inputs, *tryPartition* will either return “no” or “invalid partition”, which leads *getGalledTree* to correctly returning false.

Now let us argue the complexity. Let us first analyze the recursive search tree R created by the algorithm, where each node of R corresponds to a call to *getGalledTree*. We show by induction on the height of R that R contains at most $3 \cdot \max(1, |\mathcal{C}|)$ nodes. As a base case, when R has height 0, it is a terminal case with $1 \leq 3$ node, in which case our claim holds (even if \mathcal{C} is empty). So assume that R has higher height. Thus \mathcal{C} is non-empty. If \mathcal{C} has a maximal compatible character C , then we make recursive calls on disjoint strict subsets $\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2$ of \mathcal{C} , none of which contains C . If $\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2$ are non-empty, by induction the number of nodes of the recursion tree is at most $3|\mathcal{C}_1| + 3|\mathcal{C}_2| + 1$ (counting the

root), which is at most $3(|\mathcal{C}| - 1) + 1 \leq 3|\mathcal{C}|$ since $|\mathcal{C}_1| + |\mathcal{C}_2| < |\mathcal{C}|$. If, say, \mathcal{C}_1 is empty but not \mathcal{C}_2 (or vice-versa), the number of nodes in the recursion tree is at most $1 + 3|\mathcal{C}_2| + 1 < 1 + 3(|\mathcal{C}| - 1) + 1 \leq 3|\mathcal{C}|$. If both $\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2$ are empty, the recursion tree has 3 nodes, which is at most $3|\mathcal{C}|$.

If no maximal compatible \mathcal{C} exists, the algorithm makes recursive calls on \mathcal{C}_v sets in *tryPartition*, either when it receives $\{A_1, A_2\}$ or $\{B_1, B_2\}$. Suppose that recursive calls are made when $\{A_1, A_2\}$ is received. Again, we observe that we either return “yes” or “no”, and then *getGalledTree* exits without attempting $\{B_1, B_2\}$. It thus suffices to count the recursive calls in one call of *tryPartition*, on disjoint subsets \mathcal{C}_v of \mathcal{C} (which are non-empty since this is checked by the algorithm). Note that these subsets do not contain A . Hence, the number of nodes in R is at most

$$\sum_{v \in V(T)} 3|\mathcal{C}_v| + 1 \leq 3(|\mathcal{C}| - 1) + 1 \leq 3|\mathcal{C}|$$

since all the \mathcal{C}_v 's are disjoint and none of them contains A from \mathcal{C} . If instead some recursive calls are made when $\{B_1, B_2\}$ is the input to *tryPartition*, we can repeat the same analysis and reach the same conclusion. This proves our claim.

It thus only remains to analyze the time needed to handle one node of the recursion tree. Recall that n is the number of taxa. Testing compatibility of two characters requires computing set operations in time $O(n)$. Finding a maximal compatible character, or a pair of incompatible maximal characters, can be achieved by testing compatibility between each pair of characters, taking a total time of $O(n|\mathcal{C}|^2)$. This also allows finding A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2 in the same complexity.

During one recursion, we run *tryPartition* at most once, say on A_1, A_2 . Computing \mathcal{X} can be done in time $O(n|\mathcal{C}|)$ by computing two intersections for each character against A_1, A_2 . Testing the chain property can be done in time $O(n|\mathcal{X}|) = O(n|\mathcal{C}|)$ by sorting the \mathcal{X} 's by size (using e.g. bucket sort) and verifying the inclusions. It is straightforward to construct a tree T in time $O(n|\mathcal{C}|^2)$ from the forced clades \mathcal{C}_F (or decide that it does not exist) by relating them by set inclusion and building the corresponding tree top-down from the maximal clades to the minimal ones. Checking the “same parent” condition and building the \mathcal{C}_v sets is easily seen to not take more than $O(n|\mathcal{C}|^2)$ time.

Overall, we spend time $O(n|\mathcal{C}|^2)$ in one call to *getGalledTree* and *tryPartition*. Since the recursion tree has $O(|\mathcal{C}|)$ nodes, the total time is $O(n|\mathcal{C}|^3)$.